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Hair quality attributes of *Camelus dromedarius*

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Although the hair production trait in camel (*Camelus dromedarius*) is of secondary importance as compared to draught power, but the fibre especially from younger age group is soft and fine quality (Singh 1966) and is widely used in rural cottage industry of Rajasthan and Gujarat for preparation of daries, bags, bhaklas etc. (Sahani and Khanna 1993). The preliminary results of camel hair blends with wool, silk waste and polyester have shown encouraging results

(Gupta *et al.* 1987, 1989). Thus the assessment of fibre quality attributes of various age groups, body sites of camels and breeds is of primary importance in exploiting the hair production potential and quality of fibre for the future utility of camel fibres in the form of blends with other fibres and its uses.

Hair samples (127) from 17 yearling camel calves and 15 camels of 3-4 years of age from Bikaneri, Jaisalmeri and

Table 1. Breed, sex, site and age group-wise LSQ means of hair attributes of dromedary camels

	Staple length (cm)	Staple diameter μ $\pm$ SE (n)	Mean fibre Pure	Least square Hetero	Mean fibre diameter (μ)			Percentage of fibre		
					Hairy	Kemp	Pure	Hetero	Hairy	Kemp
Breed	**	**	**	**	**	NS	NS	NS	*	**
Bikaneri	6.89 $\pm$ 0.20 (68)	27.22 $\pm$ 0.37 (68)	20.41 $\pm$ 0.41 (68)	26.48 $\pm$ 0.37 (68)	37.31 $\pm$ 0.69 (68)	67.54 $\pm$ 1.08 (66)	41.50 $\pm$ 0.31 (68)	36.84 $\pm$ 0.58 (68)	18.14 $\pm$ 0.62 (68)	3.61 $\pm$ 0.27 (66)
Jaisalmeri	6.29 $\pm$ 0.23 (51)	27.45 $\pm$ 0.43 (51)	22.06 $\pm$ 0.47 (51)	26.04 $\pm$ 0.43 (51)	40.03 $\pm$ 0.79 (51)	68.25 $\pm$ 2.53 (15)	40.62 $\pm$ 0.82 (51)	37.84 $\pm$ 0.67 (51)	20.56 $\pm$ 0.72 (51)	2.22 $\pm$ 0.41 (15)
Kachchhi	4.97 $\pm$ 0.64 (8)	30.99 $\pm$ 1.16 (8)	23.53 $\pm$ 1.27 (8)	3.30 $\pm$ 1.17 (8)	45.65 $\pm$ 2.15 (8)	-	43.49 $\pm$ 2.22 (8)	38.60 $\pm$ 1.82 (8)	17.68 $\pm$ 1.94 (8)	-
Sex	*	**	**	**	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS
Male	5.72 $\pm$ 0.25 (68)	27.81 $\pm$ 0.45 (68)	21.14 $\pm$ 0.49 (68)	27.57 $\pm$ 0.45 (68)	40.37 $\pm$ 0.83 (68)	67.99 $\pm$ 1.53 (42)	40.67 $\pm$ 0.86 (68)	38.58 $\pm$ 0.70 (68)	19.01 $\pm$ 0.75 (68)	3.06 $\pm$ 0.25 (42)
Female	6.38 $\pm$ 0.31 (59)	29.30 $\pm$ 0.56 (59)	22.86 $\pm$ 0.62 (59)	29.64 $\pm$ 0.57 (59)	41.63 $\pm$ 1.24 (59)	67.80 $\pm$ 1.89 (39)	43.07 $\pm$ 1.08 (59)	36.94 $\pm$ 0.88 (59)	18.57 $\pm$ 0.94 (59)	2.77 $\pm$ 0.31 (39)
Site	**	**	**	**	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Shoulder	4.69 $\pm$ 0.35 (32)	27.85 $\pm$ 0.63 (32)	21.80 $\pm$ 0.69 (32)	27.29 $\pm$ 0.63 (32)	40.23 $\pm$ 1.17 (32)	68.17 $\pm$ 2.16 (21)	41.97 $\pm$ 1.21 (32)	37.30 $\pm$ 0.99 (32)	19.56 $\pm$ 1.06 (32)	2.38 $\pm$ 0.35 (21)
Mid-side	4.11 $\pm$ 0.35 (32)	26.73 $\pm$ 0.63 (32)	20.74 $\pm$ 0.69 (32)	26.30 $\pm$ 0.63 (32)	39.04 $\pm$ 1.17 (32)	67.82 $\pm$ 2.33 (19)	41.81 $\pm$ 1.21 (32)	37.25 $\pm$ 0.99 (32)	19.65 $\pm$ 1.06 (32)	2.71 $\pm$ 0.38 (19)
Hump	11.60 $\pm$ 0.35 (31)	31.18 $\pm$ 0.64 (31)	24.41 $\pm$ 0.70 (31)	31.70 $\pm$ 0.64 (31)	42.15 $\pm$ 1.19 (31)	68.86 $\pm$ 2.05 (22)	40.22 $\pm$ 1.23 (31)	38.34 $\pm$ 1.00 (31)	19.29 $\pm$ 1.07 (31)	3.22 $\pm$ 0.33 (22)
Neck	3.80 $\pm$ 0.35 (32)	28.45 $\pm$ 0.63 (32)	21.06 $\pm$ 0.69 (32)	29.14 $\pm$ 0.64 (32)	42.56 $\pm$ 1.17 (32)	66.73 $\pm$ 2.20 (19)	43.48 $\pm$ 1.21 (32)	38.14 $\pm$ 0.99 (32)	16.66 $\pm$ 1.06 (32)	3.36 $\pm$ 0.36 (19)
Age	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	N.S.	*
1 Year	5.56 $\pm$ 0.30 (67)	25.66 $\pm$ 0.55 (67)	20.08 $\pm$ 0.61 (67)	26.16 $\pm$ 0.55 (67)	36.27 $\pm$ 1.02 (67)	58.50 $\pm$ 1.36 (52)	45.18 $\pm$ 1.06 (67)	34.57 $\pm$ 0.87 (67)	18.29 $\pm$ 0.92 (67)	3.33 $\pm$ 0.22 (52)
4 Year	6.55 $\pm$ 0.25 (60)	31.45 $\pm$ 0.46 (60)	23.93 $\pm$ 0.51 (60)	31.05 $\pm$ 0.47 (60)	45.72 $\pm$ 0.86 (60)	77.29 $\pm$ 2.09 (29)	38.56 $\pm$ 0.89 (60)	40.95 $\pm$ 0.73 (60)	19.29 $\pm$ 0.78 (60)	2.50 $\pm$ 0.34 (29)
Over all	6.05 $\pm$ 0.23 (127)	28.55 $\pm$ 0.42 (127)	22.00 $\pm$ 0.47 (127)	28.61 $\pm$ 0.43 (127)	41.00 $\pm$ 0.79 (127)	67.90 $\pm$ 1.40 (81)	41.87 $\pm$ 0.81 (127)	37.76 $\pm$ 0.66 (127)	18.79 $\pm$ 0.71 (127)	2.91 $\pm$ 0.23 (81)

N.B. : * P<0.05**P<0.01 N.S.= Not significant.

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Kachchhi maintained at the NRC on Camel, Bikaner were collected. The hair samples of annual clip were collected from

4 major body sites, viz. shoulder, mid-side, hump and neck region during March. The samples were analyzed for fibre diameter, staple length and percentage of fibre types, viz. pure, hetero, hairy and kemp. The staple length was measured before washing of the hair samples. The hair samples were washed thoroughly in petrol, dried and further processed for evaluating mean fibre diameter and percentage of hair types. The hair samples were mixed thoroughly to prepare a representative sample of each and then slides were prepared after proper sectioning. The slides were examined under the Ermascope at 500X magnification for measuring fibre diameter and assessing the fibre types based on medullation percentage. In each slide 300 observations were recorded to minimize the error. The data were analyzed using mixed model least square and maximum likely hood programme (Harvey 1987).

The fibre quality attributes, viz. staple length, mean fibre diameter and percentage of fibre types are presented in Table 1. Bikaneri camels indicated higher staple length followed by Jaisalmeri and Kachchhi and the breed, site and age effect were significant ($P<0.01$). Sex effect was also significant ($P<0.05$). The hump region had the highest staple length of 11.60 cm followed by shoulder, mid-side and neck region. The overall staple length in indigenous dromedary camel was 6.05 cm. The average fibre diameter of camel hair ranged from 27.22 μ to 31.45 μ in 1 to 4 years age groups. Gupta *et al.* (1989) reported large variability in mean fibre diameter of camel hair ranging from 26-38 μ . Least-square analysis indicated significant effect of breed, sex, site and age for mean fibre diameter ($P<0.01$). The lowest fibre diameter was observed in yearling camel calves indicating fine quality of fibre, while highest fibre diameter of 30.99 μ was observed in Kachchhi breed.

The mean fibre diameter values were also estimated for different fibre types, viz. pure, hetero, hairy and kemp and compared for breed, sex, site and age effect. The lowest fibre diameter was observed for pure fibres (20.08 μ to 24.41 μ) while highest for kemp. Least-square analysis indicated significant effect ($P<0.01$) of breed, sex, site and age for mean fibre diameter of pure and hetero fibres while for hairy fibres mean fibre diameter had significant effect on breed, age

($P<0.01$) and site ($P<0.05$). Similarly for kempy fibres mean fibre diameter was nonsignificant among breed, sex and sites while age had significant effect ($P<0.01$) as expected. Thus mean fibre diameter of pure and hetero types indicated good prospect for preparation of blends with natural or synthetic fibres. The variability in mean fibre diameter among various breeds indicated scope for further improvement through selection.

Based on medullation the fibres were graded into different types and thereafter the percentage for different types were calculated. Least-square analysis for percentage of fibre types indicated age having significant effect on pure, hetero and kempy types. For percentage of hairy fibres breed effect was significant. The percentage of kemp fibres revealed significant effect of breed and age. Comparison of per cent of fibre types indicated maximum percentage of pure fibres among one year camel calves (45.18%) which revealed superior fine quality fibres from yearling camel calves. The result also indicated overall percentage of fibre types pure, hetero, hairy and kemp to be 41.87, 37.76, 18.79 and 2.91% respectively.

Fibre quality results indicated scope for preparation of blends of camel hair with other natural and synthetic fibres and also production of fabrics. The data indicated scope for further improvement of hair quality attributes and a wide scope for its utility in addition to its traditional uses under village conditions.

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